

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization INSECT RESISTANCE

Potential donors for brown planthopper (BPH) resistance

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Of 185 rice accessions from the Madhya Pradesh (India) germplasm collection screened at IRRI for resistance to BPH (standard seedbox screening technique), 18 were resistant.

Each seedling was infested with 7-10 second- to third-instar BPH biotype 1 nymphs at 7 d after seeding. Damage was scored on the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 1-9 scale.

Aolesar, Jhili, and Banda were resistant. Akkalpom, Bhondu parewa, Cross 116, Dubraj, Dudga, Garrakath, Gathwan, Gobindbhog, Haruna dubraj, Hiranakhi, Jawphool, Aagyasal, Aagyasar, Assamchudi, and Makarkam were moderately resistant. Susceptible cultivars died 8-9 d after infestation.

Aolesar, Cross 116, Dudga, Haruma dubraj, Jhili, Aagyasal, and Aagyasar also are resistant to bacterial blight. □

Multiple resistance of BG367-3 to major insect pests and diseases

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In the 1981 IRTP, BG367-3 (BG280-1-2/Ptb 33), a short-duration culture from Sri Lanka, was moderately resistant to rice leafhopper (LF) at IRRI and Tirur. From 1982 to 1986, BG367-3 was evaluated against other insect pests and diseases at Tirur.

BG367-3 was resistant to blast (BI) and moderately resistant to tungro (RTV), brown spot, gall midge, hispa,

between plants. The recommended 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha was applied.

IR32358-54-2-3-3 and IR32419-28-3-1-3 flowered the earliest, at 87 d after seeding (DAS) (see table). All other entries flowered 90-107 DAS; check CO 43 flowered 101 DAS. Ten lines yielded more than 6 t/ha.

Leaf yellowing due to RTV and soil problems caused very heavy damage to samba and thaladi crops in 1984. All

the test entries were exposed under field conditions and scored for leaf yellowing reaction. All IRRI lines were free from leaf yellowing and two lines showed resistance.

Entries IR32358-54-2-3-3 and IR28228-112-2-3-3-3 were susceptible to neck blast and IR31809-67-2-3 and IR32823-88-2-3 were susceptible to helminthosporiose. □

Yield performance of IRRI lines and their reactions to diseases.

Breeding line	Days to 50% flowering	Yield (t/ha)	Helminthosporiose	Bacterial blight	Sheath rot	Grain discoloration
IR13525-43-2-3-1-3-2 (IR62)	94	7.4	3	3	3	1
IR32358-32-2-3-3	96	3.0	1	3	0	1
IR32358-54-2-3-3 ^a	86	3.2	1	3	3	1
IR32419-28-3-1-3	87	6.5	1	3	3	0
IR25604-99-1-3-2-2	94	3.7	3	0	3	3
IR25619-75-2-3-2-3	100	6.9	3	0	3	3
IR27313-67-1-2	98	8.6	5	1	3	1
IR27325-53-2	98	5.6	3	3	3	3
IR28222-9-2-2-2-2	97	4.1	5	3	3	5
IR328224-3-2-3-2	97	4.1	3	5	3	3
IR28226-24-1-2-3-2	96	4.0	5	3	0	0
IR28228-96-3-2-1-3	99	4.2	5	3	3	3
IR28228-106-1-2-3-2	90	6.2	3	1	1	3
IR28228-112-2-3-3-3 ^a	95	4.2	5	3	1	3
IR28228-119-2-3-1-1	97	3.7	3	3	3	3
IR29519-116-2-2-2	91	5.4	3	3	1	1
IR29519-135-3-3-2	101	6.0	3	1	0	3
IR29519-157-1-2-1	91	3.0	5	5	3	3
IR29522-4-2-3	92	7.1	5	1	3	5
IR29668-34-1-1-2	103	3.8	3	1	3	3
IR29723-7-1-1-2	104	4.2	3	3	3	3
IR29723-143-3-2-1	107	4.0	5	5	1	3
IR29723-163-3-2-2	91	5.8	3	3	1	1
IR331805-20-1-3-3	91	6.1	3	5	3	1
IR31811-35-3-3-2	102	6.3	3	5	3	1
IR31827-80-3-3-2	102	2.1	3	3	3	3
IR31836-10-1-2-2	98	2.8	3	5	3	3
IR31836-42-1-3-2	101	5.2	5	3	3	3
IR31838-63-2-2-2	99	1.4	3	1	5	5
IR31855-69-1-2-3	91	4.4	3	3	3	3
IR31867-1-2-3-3	100	3.0	3	1	5	1
IR31867-4-3-3-3	101	4.9	5	3	3	3
IR31892-46-3-2 ^b	93	1.9	3	5	5	3
IR31901-17-1-2-2 ^b	103	1.8	3	3	5	3
IR31917-31-3-2-3	94	8.1	3	5	3	1
IR31917-96-3-3-1	105	5.4	5	3	3	3
IR31809-67-2-3	98	4.0	7	3	3	5
IR32822-36-1-3	98	3.1	5	3	3	1
IR32823-1-1-3	100	1.2	5	3	3	3
IR32823-22-1-3	104	2.2	3	3	3	3
IR32823-88-2-2	104	6.3	7	0	3	3
IR32830-23-2-2	101	2.1	3	3	5	5
IR32848-36-2-2	102	2.0	3	1	1	1
IR33059-120-2-1	103	2.0	5	5	3	3
IR34583-38-3	102	3.8	3	1	3	3
CO 43 ^a	101	4.8	3	3	5	3

^aAll entries scored 0 for blast except IR32358-54-2-3-3 and IR28228-112-2-3-3-3, which scored 7.

^bAll entries had a leaf yellowing score of 0 except IR31892-46-3-2 and IR31901-17-1-2-2, which scored 3. The check CO 43 scored 7.